

PRISMA SYSTEMATIC REVIEW PROTOCOL

TITLE	Mapping Research Ethics Frameworks in Philippine Higher Education: A PRISMA Systematic Review of Policies Concerning Indigenous Peoples
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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS	J.T. Haramain: Conceptualization, protocol development, search strategy, screening, data extraction, synthesis, drafting. A. Salapa: Methodological consultation, validation of screening and appraisal procedures, guidance on review design, critical revision of the manuscript
PROTOCOL VERSION/DATE	Version 1- November 2025
ABSTRACT	This protocol describes a PRISMA 2020–compliant systematic review that will map and analyze research ethics policies and governance frameworks relevant to Indigenous Peoples in Philippine higher education. The review will search international and local academic databases and grey-literature sources to identify institutional policies, national directives, and guidance documents describing ethical procedures, consent mechanisms (including FPIC), and Indigenous Knowledge Systems (IKS) considerations. Eligible materials (1997–2025) include institutional ethics manuals, CHED and NCIP issuances, peer-reviewed articles, and credible grey literature. Quality appraisal will use adapted CASP and JBI tools. Data will be extracted using a structured form and synthesized thematically into policy maps and gap analyses. Findings will inform a contextual model for inclusive research ethics in Philippine universities and produce recommendations for institutional policy reform and capacity-building. Limitations include possible gaps from inaccessible or unpublished policies, language restrictions, and single-author screening.
1. BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE	Research with Indigenous communities raises ethical issues that differ from mainstream individual-centered protocols: the need to recognize collective consent, cultural protocols, community benefit, and data sovereignty (Tuhivai Smith, 2012; Kukutai & Taylor, 2016). The Philippines has legal instruments that affirm Indigenous rights — notably the Indigenous Peoples’ Rights Act (RA 8371) — and national bodies (e.g., NCIP) that issue FPIC guidelines. Yet HEI research ethics governance varies in how these obligations are interpreted and operationalized within institutional review processes (Johnston, Ritchie, & Halseth, 2018; Battiste, 2013). A

	systematic mapping of existing policies and governance frameworks is necessary to identify patterns, gaps, and promising practices that can guide universities toward culturally grounded and ethically robust research with Indigenous Peoples.
2. OBJECTIVES	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To identify and map research ethics policies, institutional frameworks, and governance documents in Philippine higher education that concern research with Indigenous Peoples (IPs). 2. To examine how these policies address Indigenous Knowledge Systems (IKS), Free, Prior, and Informed Consent (FPIC), data ownership/sovereignty, benefit-sharing, and community participation. 3. To compare institutional and national policies against international Indigenous research ethics standards. 4. To synthesize gaps and formulate recommendations for more inclusive, context-sensitive institutional research ethics frameworks.
3. REVIEW QUESTIONS	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What institutional and national research ethics policies currently govern research involving Indigenous Peoples in Philippine higher education? 2. How do these policies address FPIC, IKS integration, data governance, and community participation? 3. Where are the principal gaps or inconsistencies between institutional practice and national/international Indigenous ethics guidance?
4. METHODS	
4.1 Review Design	The review will follow PRISMA 2020 reporting and conduct guidance (Page et al., 2021). Protocol registration will be completed in the Zenodo prior to database searching.
4.2 Eligibility Criteria	<p>Inclusion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Document types: institutional policies/IRB/REB guidelines, CHED/NCIP/other government issuances, peer-reviewed empirical or conceptual articles, reviews, theses/dissertations, and credible technical reports. • Focus: documents that discuss research ethics, governance, or procedures for research that affects Indigenous Peoples, or that address integration of IKS in research ethics. • Geographic scope: Philippines (primary). International comparative documents included when they inform institutional frameworks or best practices. • Timeframe: 1997–2025 (1997 marks RA 8371/IPRA). • Language: English or Filipino (if full text accessible). <p>Exclusion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Editorials, opinion pieces without policy/empirical content.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documents unrelated to higher-education research ethics (e.g., general social policy, clinical trials with no Indigenous focus). • Items with no accessible full text.
4.3 Information Sources and Search Strategy	<p>The search will combine controlled vocabulary and free-text terms and be adapted per database. Databases and sources to be searched:</p> <p>International academic databases: Scopus; Web of Science Core Collection; PubMed/MEDLINE; ERIC; ProQuest Central; ScienceDirect; JSTOR; SAGE Journals; Taylor & Francis; Wiley Online Library.</p> <p>Philippine and regional sources: Philippine E-Journals; HERDIN (DOST-PCHRD); ASEAN Citation Index; CHED and NCIP websites; major Philippine HEI repositories and IRB pages (e.g., UP, Ateneo, DLSU, MSU).</p> <p>Grey literature and policy sources: Google Scholar (first 200 results screened), NCIP and CHED publications, Zenodo/Zenodo-hosted technical reports, NGO publications (e.g., Tebtebba).</p> <p>Sample search string (adapt and refine per database):</p> <p>(“Indigenous Peoples” OR “Indigenous Knowledge Systems” OR “Indigenous communities” OR “traditional knowledge”) AND (“research ethics” OR “ethics framework” OR “ethics guidelines” OR “Institutional Review Board” OR “IRB” OR “REB” OR “ethics committee”) AND (“higher education” OR “university” OR “college” OR “HEI”) AND (Philippines OR Filipino)</p> <p>Search logs will record database, date searched, exact search string, filters, and number of hits. Reference lists of included documents will be hand-searched for additional materials.</p>
4.4 Study Selection Process	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Export search results to Zotero and remove duplicates. 2. Title/abstract screening against eligibility criteria; record decisions. 3. Retrieve full texts of potentially eligible records; apply full-text inclusion/exclusion criteria. 4. Single-author screening will be used, with problematic cases reviewed in consultation with a methodological advisor and reasons for inclusion/exclusion documented. A PRISMA 2020 flow diagram will show the process.
4.5 Data Extraction	<p>A standardized data extraction form will be used (Excel). Key extracted fields:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citation (author / issuing body) • Year

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Document type (policy, guideline, article, report) • Origin (institution, national agency) • Jurisdiction/coverage (institutional, national) • Key ethical components (FPIC, consent type, data governance, authorship, benefit-sharing) • Reference to IKS or Indigenous epistemologies (explicit, implicit, none) • Mechanisms for Indigenous participation in REB/IRB (representation, consultation) • Implementation and enforcement mechanisms (training, sanctions, monitoring) • Stated limitations, implementation notes, or evaluations • Direct quotes of policy language (where relevant) • Notes on alignment with IPRA / UNDRIP / international frameworks <p>Pilot extraction will be conducted on 5 documents and the form refined.</p>
<p>4.6 Quality Appraisal</p>	<p>Documents will be appraised using adapted tools depending on document type:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CASP (Critical Appraisal Skills Programme) qualitative checklist (adapted) for qualitative studies and articles (CASP, 2022). • JBI Text and Opinion Checklist for policy documents and guidelines. • For grey literature, the AACODS checklist (Authority, Accuracy, Coverage, Objectivity, Date, Significance) will be used. <p>Appraisal will focus on clarity, evidence base, cultural sensitivity, stakeholder involvement, and applicability. Each document will receive a quality rating (High / Moderate / Low) to inform sensitivity analyses.</p>
<p>4.7 Data Synthesis</p>	<p>Considering the heterogeneity of document types, researchers will use a narrative synthesis with thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke approach). Steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Code extracted items inductively for recurring policy components (e.g., FPIC procedures, data governance, community participation). 2. Group codes into higher-order themes describing how institutions conceptualize and operationalize Indigenous research ethics. 3. Compare and contrast institutional-level policies with national-level directives (NCIP, CHED) and international standards (OCAP/CARE/AIATSIS/TCPS2). 4. Produce a policy-map table showing which HEIs have which components, a gap table (missing elements common across institutions), and examples of exemplary policy language.

	5. Identify actionable recommendations for institutional policy revision and capacity building.
4.8 Reporting and Prisma Flow Diagram	The final manuscript will follow PRISMA 2020 reporting items. Supplementary materials will include the full search strategies, extraction table, appraisal scores, and the PRISMA flow diagram.
5. ETHICS AND DISSEMINATION	No primary data or human participants are involved; therefore, formal ethics approval is not required. The review will be disseminated through peer-reviewed journals (target journals listed below), conference presentations, and open-access archiving in Zenodo. Findings and policy briefs will also be shared with CHED, NCIP, and higher education institutions to support inclusive research ethics reform.
6. TIMELINE	Protocol finalization & OSF registration: November 2025 Database searching: Weeks 1–2 after registration Screening (titles/abstracts): Weeks 3 -4 Full-text screening & appraisal: Week 5 Data extraction & synthesis: Week 6 Manuscript drafting: Week 7 Submission to journal: Week 8
7. TARGET JOURNALS	Research Ethics; International Journal of Educational Development; Asia Pacific Education Review; Higher Education Research & Development; Journal of Empirical Research on Human Research Ethics; Australian Journal of Indigenous Education (AJIE); WINHEC Journal; SAGE Open; World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews (WJARR). Final target shall be selected after manuscript drafting to tailor scope and formatting.
8. LIMITATIONS	Institutional policies not publicly accessible may be missed, creating potential gaps in coverage. Single-author screening increases the risk of selection bias; to mitigate this, a methodological advisor will be consulted on ambiguous cases. Language limitations confined to English and Filipino may exclude some local-language materials. In addition, unpublished internal guidelines or informal practices within higher education institutions may not be captured, which could limit the comprehensiveness of the synthesis.
9. REGISTRATION STATEMENT	This protocol will be archived and disseminated through Zenodo, an open-access research repository, prior to the initiation of database searches.
10. DATA AVAILABILITY	All extracted data, search logs, and supplementary files will be archived and made publicly accessible through the Zenodo repository. Version control will be maintained, and any updates or additions will be transparently documented within the Zenodo record to ensure reproducibility and accountability.
11. AMENDMENTS	Any protocol changes will be logged and timestamped and made publicly accessible within the Zenodo record to ensure accountability and reproducibility.

12. RISK OF BIAS ACROSS SOURCES	We will assess risk of bias across sources by examining potential publication bias, particularly the absence of institutional policies that may not be publicly accessible. Grey literature will be critically evaluated for comprehensiveness, authority, and objectivity to ensure balanced representation. Any gaps or limitations in source availability will be transparently reported in the final synthesis.
13. CONFIDENCE IN EVIDENCE	Confidence in the synthesized findings will be assessed using the GRADE-CERQual (Confidence in the Evidence from Reviews of Qualitative Research) approach. CERQual evaluates four domains: methodological limitations, coherence of findings, adequacy of data, and relevance to the review question. Each synthesized theme or policy component will be assigned a confidence rating (high, moderate, low, or very low). This process will ensure transparency in how conclusions are drawn and highlight areas where evidence is strong versus where caution is warranted.
14. RECORD MANAGEMENT	Search results and screening decisions will be organized and managed in Zotero, with duplicates removed and inclusion/exclusion decisions documented. Data extraction will be conducted using structured Excel sheets with version control to ensure accuracy and traceability. Final datasets, logs, and supplementary files will be archived in Zenodo for open access and reproducibility.
15. FUNDING	This review is conducted without external funding. All activities, including protocol development, database searching, screening, and synthesis, are supported by the authors' own institutional affiliations and resources.
16. CONFLICT OF INTEREST	The authors declare that they have no competing interests. No financial, institutional, or personal relationships exist that could be perceived to influence the conduct or reporting of this review.
17. REFERENCES	<p>Australian Institute of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies (AIATSIS). (2020). <i>AIATSIS Code of Ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research</i>. Canberra, ACT: AIATSIS.</p> <p>Battiste, M. (2013). <i>Decolonizing education: Nourishing the learning spirit</i>. Saskatoon, SK: Purich Publishing.</p> <p>Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP). (2022). <i>CASP qualitative studies checklist</i>. https://casp-uk.net/casp-tools-checklists/</p> <p>Johnston, E., Ritchie, L., & Halseth, R. (2018). <i>Indigenous cultural safety: An environmental scan of cultural competency and safety in health education</i>. Prince George, BC: National Collaborating Centre for Indigenous Health.</p> <p>Kukutai, T., & Taylor, J. (Eds.). (2016). <i>Indigenous data sovereignty: Towards an agenda</i>. Canberra, ACT: ANU Press. https://doi.org/10.22459/IDS.04.2016</p>

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